

Original Research

Analysis of the Implementation of the SAKTI Application and PPNPN in Work Units in Mataram City

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Abstract

This study analyzes the influence of system quality, information quality, and service quality on user satisfaction and net benefits in the use of the SAKTI and PPNPN applications in Mataram City's government work units. Using a quantitative approach and survey method, data were collected from 120 users and analyzed through Structural Equation Modeling with Partial Least Squares (PLS-SEM). Results indicate that system quality does not significantly affect user satisfaction, while information quality and service quality have positive and significant effects. Additionally, user satisfaction significantly enhances net benefits, such as increased efficiency and productivity. These findings suggest that improving information accuracy and service responsiveness is more impactful for user satisfaction than system functionality alone.

Keywords: Information quality, net benefits, SAKTI, service quality, system quality, user satisfaction.

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Introduction

The Government of Indonesia has initiated national development programs to enhance quality across various sectors and strengthen competitiveness in the VUCA (Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, and Ambiguous) era (Aribowo & Wirapraja, 2018; Setyawan et al., 2017). One key initiative in the financial sector is the implementation of the Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS). Additionally, the government promotes e-government to improve efficiency, effectiveness, transparency, and accountability, as mandated by Presidential Instruction No. 3 of 2003 (Inpres, 2003).

Currently, over 24,400 applications support e-government implementation as per the Presidential Instruction. However, the excessive number of applications is deemed inefficient and resource-draining (Said, 2022). To address this, the government issued Minister of Finance Regulation No. 171/PMK.05/2021 on the Implementation of the SAKTI System, aimed at simplifying and integrating financial systems within the government.

The SAKTI system, developed by the Ministry of Finance, aims to streamline and reduce the number of applications used. It is integrated with various unit-based applications, enhancing government financial management efficiency. One unit-based application integrated with SAKTI is PPNPN, developed by the Directorate General of Treasury to manage payments for Non-Civilian Government Employees (PPNPN). Since 2022, PPNPN has been officially integrated with SAKTI, further enhancing efficiency and accuracy in payment management for PPNPN (Election Supervisory Committee of Pacitan Regency, 2022).

The SAKTI system is not new to accounting recording and reporting in government agencies. It has been piloted since 2015, as outlined in Minister of Finance Regulation No. 223/PMK.95/2015. However, with the implementation of Minister of Finance Regulation No. 171/PMK.05/2021, its use has become mandatory for all government agencies managing the state budget or central government funds (Rahayuningtyas, 2022). Although recently made mandatory nationwide, the SAKTI system has been used by various units in Mataram for several years. Regular evaluations are necessary to ensure optimal functionality and enhance efficiency, effectiveness, transparency, and accountability.

Information system evaluations can be conducted using various models. For example, Nugroho and Lestyowati (2020) used the PIECES Framework to classify problems, opportunities, and directives to identify key issues and provide solutions. Meanwhile, Prabowo (2017) employed the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), focusing on the acceptance, adoption, and use of the information system.

Three key theories can be used to analyze the implementation of the SAKTI and PPNPN applications in Mataram's work units. The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) emphasizes that behavioral intent, shaped by individual attitudes and subjective norms, is a primary factor in technology adoption. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) highlights the importance of perceived benefits and ease of use as key predictors of acceptance. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) extends TRA by incorporating

perceived behavioral control, which reflects an individual's perceived ability and resources to use technology. Together, these theories explain that positive attitudes, social support, and perceived control significantly influence users' intentions and actions in adopting SAKTI and PPNPN applications, while also shedding light on factors that can facilitate or hinder technology acceptance in the workplace.

This study uses the Delone and McLean Information System Success Model to analyze the success of implementing the SAKTI and PPNPN applications. This model was chosen due to its widespread use in similar research, such as by Amriani and Iskandar (2019), Deny and Andry (2018), Hadi (2022), Iskandar and Amriani (2021), At-tamimi and Siregar (2021), and Mu'minah and Metalica (2022). Additionally, it is considered a comprehensive yet simple framework (Jogiyanto, 2007). In this study, the model was modified as suggested by Amriani and Iskandar (2019), who argued that the system usage variable (use), as a behavior, is not suitable for causal models.

Based on the modified Delone and McLean Information System Success Model, the success of implementing the SAKTI and PPNPN applications will be analyzed through the relationships between variables. The assessment measures the impact of system quality, information quality, and service quality on user satisfaction, and how user satisfaction influences net benefits.

This evaluation is crucial not only to ensure smooth application use but also to understand user perceptions of system, information, and service quality. Their perceptions directly influence user satisfaction, ultimately affecting the net benefits derived from application usage. Understanding user perspectives is key to analyzing their attitudes and satisfaction with the application. The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) supports this approach by explaining how individual attitudes influence intentions and behavior in application usage.

Previous studies on the implementation of the SAKTI application in work units, including those by Hadi (2022), Pambudi et al. (2022), Nasution and Nasution (2022), Nugroho and Lestyowati (2020), At-tamimi and Siregar (2021), and Prabowo (2017), show that its implementation has been successful. The application is highly regarded for supporting government accounting and simplifying financial report preparation.

However, studies by Anwar and Hadi (2022), Iskandar and Amriani (2021), Amriani and Iskandar (2019), and Mu'minah and Metalica (2022) found that the SAKTI application implementation still faces challenges. Issues identified include lagging, limited infrastructure, and frequent maintenance, which disrupt work. As a result, the implementation is considered not fully successful. This indicates inconsistency in the implementation results of the SAKTI application across various units/agencies. Additionally, previous studies focused on the desktop version, while since 2022, the application has migrated to a web-based platform.

This change introduces novelty to the study, which evaluates the web-based SAKTI application and its integration with the PPNPN application for non-civil servant payroll. Additionally, following the recommendation of Amriani and Iskandar (2019) to broaden

the research scope, this study includes all work units in Mataram to provide a more comprehensive view of the web-based SAKTI implementation.

Table 1. Performance in Implementation of SAKTI Application and Management of PPNPN

No.	Aspect	Year 2023	Year 2024	Change
1	Number of staff who have not been trained in the SAKTI application	40 people	20 people	Decrease 50%
2	Satisfaction with system response speed	60%	50%	Decrease 10%
3	The level of effectiveness of the SAKTI application	70%	65%	Decrease 5%
4	Late payment of PPNPN	15% of PPNPN	20% of PPNPN	Increase 5%
5	PPNPN satisfaction level towards payroll process	70%	65%	Decrease 5%
6	Availability of IT infrastructure	60% of work units	50% of work units	Decrease 10%

Source: Mataram City Government Agency Performance Report (2024)

The table shows a significant change in several aspects of the SAKTI application implementation and PPNPN management from 2023 to 2024. The number of staff untrained in using the SAKTI application decreased by 50%, from 40 in 2023 to 20 in 2024. This decrease indicates improvements in training efforts. However, there remains a need to enhance understanding of the more complex features of the application, given SAKTI's strategic role in supporting financial operational efficiency in work units.

On the other hand, satisfaction with system response speed decreased by 10%, from 60% in 2023 to 50% in 2024. This decline suggests performance issues, likely due to technical factors such as unstable servers, insufficient system capacity, or other disruptions. Reduced satisfaction with response speed may affect administrative efficiency and service quality.

Furthermore, the effectiveness of the SAKTI application decreased by 5%, from 70% in 2023 to 65% in 2024. Despite progress, complaints persist regarding the application's misalignment with increasingly complex operational needs, possibly due to limited functionality or mismatched features with on-the-ground business processes.

Regarding PPNPN payment delays, there was a 5% increase, from 15% last year to 20%. This reflects issues in financial administration management despite the application being implemented. Delays may result from factors such as system integration challenges, limited resources, or suboptimal budget management.

Additionally, PPNPN satisfaction with the payroll process decreased by 5%, from 70% to 65%. This decline indicates dissatisfaction with the timeliness and transparency of

payroll. Despite expectations that the application would improve efficiency, challenges remain in accuracy and clarity of the payroll information provided to PPNPN.

Finally, IT infrastructure availability decreased by 10%, from 60% of work units in the previous year to 50%. This reflects an imbalance in infrastructure distribution, affecting the implementation of the SAKTI application. Limited IT infrastructure, particularly in remote areas, hinders optimal access and use, impacting operational effectiveness in those regions.

Overall, despite a reduction in untrained staff and efforts to enhance training, technical, administrative, and infrastructure issues remain key obstacles in the implementation of the SAKTI application and PPNPN management. The decline in satisfaction and effectiveness highlights the need for further evaluation and systematic improvements in technology integration, training, and infrastructure to achieve the desired efficiency and transparency.

The novelty of this study lies in its focus on evaluating the web-based SAKTI application, integrated with the PPNPN system for non-civil servant salary payments. This research assesses the system's migration from desktop to web-based platform since 2022, offering new insights into implementation and challenges arising from this platform shift.

Additionally, this study broadens the scope of previous research, which focused solely on desktop applications, by examining all work units in Mataram City. This aligns with prior recommendations to expand the study's scope and contributes new insights into assessing the effectiveness of the SAKTI application and PPNPN management in the context of government technology modernization.

There is a close relationship between user training, the effectiveness of the SAKTI application, system speed, the availability of information technology (IT) infrastructure, and the satisfaction and accuracy of PPNPN payments. The relationship between these variables reflects the extent to which technology system integration can support administrative efficiency and improve services to non-civil servant employees.

First, staff training shows a positive relationship with the effectiveness of application use. The number of staff who were not trained in the use of the SAKTI application decreased by 50%, from 40 people in 2023 to 20 people in 2024. This reflects an increase in human resource capacity in understanding the basics of application use. However, a 5% decrease in application effectiveness indicates that existing training is still unable to address the challenges of using more complex advanced features. Therefore, training should be more focused on a comprehensive understanding of the system, not just basic technical aspects.

Second, the effectiveness of the SAKTI application directly affects satisfaction with the payroll process. When the effectiveness of the application decreases, satisfaction with the payroll process also decreases by 5%. This shows that a system that is less than optimal in supporting financial administration processes can have a negative impact on PPNPN's perception of the accuracy, transparency, and timeliness of salary payments.

Third, the speed of the system's response also has a significant influence on administrative efficiency. Satisfaction with system response decreased from 60% to 50%, which may indicate technical issues such as slow servers, network disruptions, or insufficient system capacity. Slow system performance can prolong the processing time for administrative documents, including payroll, thereby contributing to an increase in the rate of delayed payments to PPNPN from 15% to 20%.

Furthermore, the increase in PPNPN payment delays has a negative correlation with PPNPN satisfaction levels. When payments are not made on time, this can trigger dissatisfaction as it relates to employee welfare. Thus, delays in this process serve as a direct indicator of the inefficiency of the financial administration system in place.

Another factor that affects the overall effectiveness of implementation is the availability of information technology infrastructure. Data shows that only 50% of work units had adequate infrastructure in 2024, a decrease of 10% compared to the previous year. Disparities in infrastructure provision, especially in remote areas, have led to uneven access to the SAKTI application, which ultimately affects the smooth running of the financial administration digitization process.

Literature Review

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), developed by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975), emphasizes that behavioral intention is the main predictor of a person's actions. This intention is shaped by attitudes toward behavior and subjective norms, which are individuals' perceptions of social pressure to perform or refrain from performing an action. In the context of the SAKTI and PPNPN applications, positive attitudes of civil servants toward the benefits of the application and expectations from the work environment (e.g., superiors or colleagues) determine the intention to use the application. TRA provides an initial framework for understanding that if civil servants have a strong intention, they are likely to actively use the application.

Meanwhile, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis (1989) is an extension of TRA in the context of information technology. In the implementation of the SAKTI and PPNPN applications, civil servants' perceptions of the benefits and ease of use significantly influence their attitudes, which ultimately determine their intention and behavior in using the application. TAM bridges the technical aspects of information systems with the psychological factors of users.

Furthermore, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which is a further development of TRA, adds an important construct called perceived behavioral control (PBC), which refers to an individual's perception of their ability to control or perform a behavior. In the context of application implementation, PBC includes factors such as technical support, training, infrastructure availability, and civil servants' confidence in operating the system. In other words, even if someone has a positive attitude and supportive social norms, without perceived behavioral control (e.g., due to limited internet access or lack of training), the intention to use the application may not necessarily lead to actual behavior.

These three theories complement each other in explaining the complexity of user behavior toward digital applications in a bureaucratic work environment. TRA provides the psychological foundation, TAM focuses on technology perception, and TPB emphasizes control and actual ability. By integrating all three, this study can identify the key factors influencing the adoption and utilization of the SAKTI and PPNPN applications by civil servants in Mataram City, and provide a strong basis for formulating more targeted policies.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis (1989) is an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), specifically designed to explain the adoption of information technology. In the context of implementing the SAKTI and PPNPN applications in the Mataram City work unit, TAM provides a basis for understanding why some civil servants (ASN) readily accept the system, while others encounter obstacles. If ASN perceive that the application provides tangible benefits in accelerating and simplifying administrative tasks (high PU) and is easy to operate without significant technical challenges (high PEOU), they are likely to exhibit positive attitudes and a strong desire to use it continuously.

Furthermore, as explained by Alfadda and Mahdi (2021), TAM also acknowledges the importance of users' initial experience with the system when it is first introduced. Positive experiences will shape good perceptions, which in turn strengthen intentions and actual behavior in using the system in the future. In other words, the initial success of the application's implementation—for example, through effective training, a user-friendly interface, and responsive technical support—will greatly determine the sustainability of this technology's adoption.

In other words, TAM emphasizes that to increase civil servants' acceptance of the SAKTI and PPNPN applications, agencies need to focus on two key aspects: ensuring that the applications are functionally useful and easily accessible and usable, both from a technical and psychological perspective. This theory provides strategic guidance in designing and evaluating system implementation interventions in the public sector.

Theory of Planned (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) was developed by Ajzen (1985) as an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) previously formulated by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975). TPB introduces an additional element that is important in understanding behavior, namely Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC), or the perception of control over a behavior. In the context of this study, TPB is highly relevant for understanding the psychological and social factors that influence civil servants' behavior in accepting and using the SAKTI and PPNPN applications. TPB provides a robust theoretical framework for explaining variations in application usage behavior among individuals. Some civil servants may have a positive attitude but do not use the application because they feel they lack technical ability. Conversely, others may have the technical ability but are hindered by a lack of social motivation or leadership within the agency.

By incorporating TPB into the research model, researchers can identify factors that agencies should strengthen, such as fostering positive attitudes through education, creating supportive social norms through leadership guidance, and enhancing perceived control through systematic training and technical support.

Financial Application System (SAKTI)

The Institutional Financial Application System (SAKTI) is one form of e-Government implementation in state financial management (Nasution & Nasution, 2022). SAKTI was developed as part of the Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS), which has been adopted by the Indonesian government through the State Treasury and Budget System (SPAN) at the Ministry of Finance (Diamond & Khemani, 2005).

Within the scope of work units (Satker), IFMIS is implemented through the improvement of state financial management business processes using an integrated application, namely SAKTI (Nugroho & Lestyowati, 2020). The development of SAKTI aims to simplify the financial management system in Satker by implementing an integrated database.

SAKTI is mandatory for all Satkers in state financial management. This application is designed to be used by thousands of Satkers throughout Indonesia to support budgeting and treasury business processes in a more efficient, transparent, and integrated manner.

Non-Civil Servant Government Employee Income Payment System (PPNPN)

Non-Civil Servant Government Employees (PPNPN) are temporary employees recognized by the government and state and assigned to various agencies to support work in units that require their services. The PPNPN Salary Application System is a single database-based system used to process PPNPN income payments. This system was developed by the Directorate General of Treasury using the Web-Based Payroll Application Module to ensure more integrated and efficient payroll management.

Payroll payments for PPNPN through this application have been implemented on a pilot basis at agency units (satker) within the Ministry of Finance since January 2022. Since the pilot program proceeded in accordance with regulations, the application was subsequently fully implemented across all K/L units. Effective September 19, 2022, all K/L units are required to use the PPNPN Web-Based Payroll Application Module.

Delone and McLean Information System Success Model (Delone and Mclean ISSM)

The DeLone and McLean Information System Success Model was first proposed by DeLone and McLean (1992) to measure the success of information systems (IS). This model was developed because at that time there was no integrated view of the concept of IS success in a comprehensive manner.

Before this model was introduced, various studies used different IS success indicators, making it difficult to compare studies. The DeLone and McLean Information System Success Model aims to bring these various perspectives together into a more structured

conceptual framework that can be used as a basis for evaluating the success of information systems.

System Quality

System quality refers to the measurement of information system performance, including hardware, software, and the policies and procedures that support the system. System quality is an important factor because it determines the extent to which the information needed by users can be generated, accessed, and utilized effectively through the company's information system.

According to DeLone and McLean, system quality reflects the performance of the hardware, software, policies, and procedures that support the system in providing the information needed by users. In other words, system quality encompasses not only the technological infrastructure but also the overall system design (Marakas & O'Brien, 2017). However, system quality measurement is subjective, as it depends on each user's perception of the system's ease of use, speed, reliability, and effectiveness in meeting their needs.

Information Quality

Information quality refers to the measurement of output generated by an information system (Harnowo et al., 2021). Like system quality, information quality is also subjective, depending on the user's perception of the information presented. The characteristics of information produced by information systems can vary, so measuring information quality based on user perception is important to assess the extent to which the information produced is useful and meets user needs.

Service Quality

Service quality is defined as the comparison between the expectations of information system users and their perceptions of the services received (Amriani & Iskandar, 2019b). According to the DeLone and McLean model, there are several elements that influence service quality, including assurance and empathy. Assurance refers to the extent to which an information system is able to provide reliability and a sense of security for its users. Empathy refers to the level of attention and concern the system has for the needs and experiences of users. These two elements aim to complement the measurement of information quality and system quality, so that information systems are not only assessed from a technical perspective but also from the support services provided to users (Sembiring, 2013).

User Satisfaction

User satisfaction is an overall evaluation of the experience of using an information system and the potential impact it has (DeLone & McLean, 2003). This satisfaction is related to users' perceptions of the benefits and attitudes toward the system, which can be influenced by personal characteristics.

According to Hutajulu et al. (2019), user satisfaction with information systems depends not only on the technical quality of the system, but also on how users view and perceive the benefits of the system in real terms. In other words, user satisfaction is an emotional reaction, whether positive or negative, to the benefits obtained from interacting with the information system.

Research Model

Figure 1. Research Model

Hypothesis

1. System Quality in Relation to User Satisfaction

System quality is the result of a combination of software and hardware used to process information according to user needs. Meanwhile, user satisfaction is the user's response to their experience in using the information system. This satisfaction depends on the user's perception of the extent to which the information system used has met their needs.

Various previous studies have shown that system quality has a positive effect on user satisfaction levels. This finding is supported by research by Al-Athmay et al. (2016), Aldholay et al. (2018), Almaiah and Alismaiel (2019), Alzahrani et al. (2019), Al-Zahrani (2020), Banner et al. (2018), Karlinsky-Shichor and Zviran (2016), Laumer et al. (2017), Lee and Jeon (2020), Marjanovic et al. (2016), Masunga et al. (2020), Mellouli et al. (2020), Mudzana and Maharaj (2017), Al-Rawahna et al. (2018), Oktal et al. (2016), Rana et al. (2015), Sorongan and Hidayati (2020), Stefanovic et al. (2016), Tam and Oliveira (2016), Urbina et al. (2019), Van Cauter et al. (2017), Veeramootoo et al. (2018), Wei et al. (2017), Yang Tsai et al. (2017), and Yu and Qian (2018).

The results of this study indicate that the higher the quality of the system based on user perception, the higher their level of satisfaction in using the system. With good information system quality, users can obtain the expected benefits, thereby increasing their comfort and willingness to continue using the system.

Based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), system quality influences user satisfaction through two main factors, namely Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). PU reflects the extent to which the system can improve user performance, while PEOU describes the extent to which the system is easy to use. A system with high quality, such as speed and ease of use, will enhance users' perceptions of usefulness and ease of use, ultimately having a positive impact on their satisfaction.

These two factors are interrelated, where ease of use can strengthen the perception of usefulness, which in turn further increases user satisfaction. Therefore, the researchers hypothesize that the better the system quality, the higher the level of satisfaction among SAKTI and PPNPN users. Based on the above explanation, the hypothesis that can be formulated is as follows:

H₁: System quality has a positive effect on user satisfaction.

2. Information Quality and User Satisfaction

Information quality is a measure of the output produced by an information system, including aspects such as report format (DeLone & McLean, 1992). Information quality relates to the accuracy, completeness, timeliness, and format of the information produced by the system.

Meanwhile, user satisfaction reflects users' responses to the usefulness of information system outputs and the extent to which the information obtained meets their needs (DeLone & McLean, 2003). Information quality can influence user satisfaction because accurate, complete, relevant, and timely information will improve the quality of decision-making, so that users feel the benefits of the information system.

Previous research also supports this relationship, as shown in studies conducted by Al Athmay et al. (2016), Aldholay et al. (2018), Almaiah and Alismaiel (2019), Alzahrani et al. (2019), Al-Zahrani (2020), Banner et al. (2018), Bradford et al. (2020), Laumer et al. (2017), Lee and Jeon (2020), Masri et al. (2020), Masunga et al. (2020), Mellouli et al. (2020), Mudzana and Maharaj (2017), Mujali Al-rawahna et al. (2018), Oktal et al. (2016), Rahi and Abd.Ghani (2019), Rana et al. (2015), Santa et al. (2019), Shim and Jo (2020), Sorongan and Hidayati (2020), Tam and Oliveira (2016), Urbina et al. (2019), Van Cauter et al. (2017), Wang and Teo (2020), Wei et al. (2017), Yang Tsai et al. (2017), and Yu and Qian (2018). These findings indicate that the better the quality of information according to user perception, the higher the level of user satisfaction with the information system used.

Based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), information quality has a positive and significant effect on user satisfaction. TAM states that two main factors, namely Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), directly influence users' intentions to use a technology, which ultimately impacts their satisfaction with the system.

High-quality information, characterized by accuracy, relevance, and ease of understanding, enhances PU because users feel the system provides significant benefits in improving their performance or simplifying tasks. Additionally, clear and easily

processable information enhances PEOU because users do not encounter difficulties in using the system to obtain the required information.

These two factors, PU and PEOU, contribute positively to user satisfaction, as they feel more productive and comfortable using the system. Therefore, good information quality will significantly increase user satisfaction, in line with the TAM framework that links information quality with users' perceptions of the ease and usefulness of technology. Based on this concept, this study hypothesizes that the better the quality of information produced by SAKTI and PPNPN, the higher the user satisfaction. Thus, the hypothesis that can be formulated is as follows:

H₂: Information quality has a positive effect on user satisfaction.

3. Service Quality and User Satisfaction

Parasuraman et al. (1988) define service quality as the comparison between customer expectations and their perceptions of the service actually received. Meanwhile, according to Petter et al. (2008), service quality refers to the level of support or assistance received by users from the information systems department and related personnel. This service quality encompasses aspects of competence assurance, responsiveness, and empathy from information technology (IT) staff in providing services to users.

Research by Mu'minah and Metalica (2022) shows that service quality has a positive effect on user satisfaction. This finding is in line with research conducted by Aboelmaged (2018), Almaiah and Alismaiel (2019), Alzahrani et al. (2019), Banner et al. (2018), Bradford et al. (2020), Masunga et al. (2020), Mellouli et al. (2020), Namahoot and Laohavichien (2015), Stefanovic et al. (2016), Thi et al. (2016), Urbina et al. (2019), and Van Cauter et al. (2017). The results of this study indicate that good service quality in information systems contributes to increased user satisfaction. Therefore, in developing information systems, it is important to consider the service aspects provided after the system is implemented to ensure an optimal user experience.

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), service quality has a positive effect on user satisfaction through factors that influence individual intentions and behavior. TPB explains that a person's behavior is influenced by three main elements, namely attitude toward behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

In the context of services, if the quality of service provided meets user expectations, a positive attitude toward the service will be formed, ultimately increasing user satisfaction. Additionally, subjective norms, which are the influence of the social environment or others, can reinforce user satisfaction, especially if they feel that the service received has been recognized and valued by the relevant community or group.

Furthermore, perceived behavioral control, such as ease of access to services and obtaining clear information, also plays a role in increasing user satisfaction. In other words, the better the quality of service provided, the more likely users are to feel satisfied because their needs and expectations are met. This also encourages their intention to continue using the service. Based on the above explanation, this study hypothesizes that

better service quality will have a positive effect on the satisfaction of SAKTI and PPNPN users. Therefore, the hypothesis that can be formulated is as follows:

H₃: Service quality has a positive effect on user satisfaction.

4. User Satisfaction with Net Benefits

User satisfaction in the context of information system utilization can be defined as the final feeling of pleasure that arises from the interaction between users and a system (Seddon & Kiew, 1996). Bailey and Pearson (1983) state that user satisfaction is often used as an indicator of information system success because it can be linked to various elements that constitute success in several conceptual aspects. Additionally, user satisfaction offers a broader perspective than other measures of information system success, as it reflects users' experiences and perceptions of the system's effectiveness in meeting their needs.

The sense of satisfaction users feel toward an information system with good performance can encourage them to contribute further to the organization, either through increased work effectiveness or higher achievement. As a result, the benefits obtained by the organization also increase. These findings are in line with the research of Pambudi et al. (2022) and other studies such as Al-Zahrani (2020), Bradford et al. (2020), Lee and Jeon (2020), Masunga et al. (2020), Sorongan and Hidayati (2020), Wang and Teo (2020), Aldholay et al. (2018), Almaiah and Alismaiel (2019), Alzahrani et al. (2019), Banner et al. (2018), Mudzana and Maharaj (2017), Mujali Al-rawahna et al. (2018), Urbina et al. (2019), and Yu and Qian (2018). This shows that if SAKTI and PPNPN users are satisfied with the system's capabilities, they tend to find the information system easy to use, which ultimately speeds up the completion of their work and improves their performance.

User satisfaction has a positive effect on net benefit, as explained in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which states that individual behavior is influenced by intentions formed through attitudes, subjective norms, and perceptions of behavioral control. In this context, user satisfaction reflects a positive attitude toward the use of a system or service, which in turn increases their intention to continue using it. High satisfaction encourages users to feel the net benefits of using the application or technology, whether in terms of efficiency, convenience, or results obtained.

When users are satisfied, they tend to perceive that the system they are using provides significant added value, thereby strengthening their intention to continue utilizing and supporting the sustainability of the technology's implementation. Additionally, perceived behavioral control plays a role, as satisfied users are more confident in managing and optimizing technology use to achieve better outcomes. Based on this, this study hypothesizes that the higher the level of user satisfaction, the greater the net benefits obtained from the use of SAKTI and PPNPN in supporting the performance of individual users. Therefore, the hypothesis that can be formulated is as follows:

H₄: User satisfaction has a positive effect on net benefits.

Methodology

This study uses a quantitative approach with explanatory research that is causal in nature, aiming to explain the relationship between variables through hypothesis testing. This study utilizes numerical data and analyzes it using statistical techniques to identify the cause-and-effect relationship between the variables under study.

The research was conducted in work units located in Mataram City, West Nusa Tenggara Province, which have implemented two application systems, namely SAKTI (Institutional Financial Application System) and PPNPN (Non-Civil Servant Government Employee Management). The research was conducted in November 2024, as this timeframe was deemed to represent the actual conditions of application use by operators, while also considering operational variations and workloads at the end of the fiscal year.

The population in this study consists of all SAKTI and PPNPN application operators in 48 work units in the city of Mataram. The sampling method used is saturated sampling, a technique where all members of the population are included as research samples (Sugiyono, 2017). Thus, the sample size in this study is 120 operators, all of whom are actively involved in using the SAKTI and PPNPN applications.

The primary instrument used in this study was a closed-ended questionnaire designed using a 1–5 Likert scale, ranging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree.” The questionnaire was designed to measure respondents’ perceptions of various research variable indicators, including perceptions of the ease of using the application, the benefits of using it, and its impact on work effectiveness.

The questionnaire was distributed directly (offline) to all respondents to ensure a high response rate and optimal data quality. Before distribution, the questionnaire was tested for validity and reliability through a preliminary test (pilot test).

The collected data were analyzed using the Partial Least Squares (PLS)-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method, with the assistance of SmartPLS version 4 software. SEM-PLS was chosen because it is capable of analyzing complex models with many latent variables and does not require normally distributed data.

The stages of data processing using SEM-PLS are as follows: Outer Model Testing (Measurement Model), Inner Model Testing (Structural Model) serta Uji Hypothesis

Results and Discussion

Measurement Model Evaluation (External)

Convergent Validity

Table 1. AVE dan Communalilty

Variable	AVE	Communalilty
System Quality (X1)	0,685	0,827
Information Quality (X2)	0,742	0,861
Service Quality (X3)	0,692	0,832
User Satisfaction (Z)	0,839	0,916
Net Benefit (Y)	0,574	0,758

Based on the results of data processing using the Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) approach through SmartPLS version 4 software, convergent validity testing was conducted by referring to the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Communalilty values of each construct. The analysis results indicate that all constructs in the model, namely System Quality (X1), Information Quality (X2), Service Quality (X3), User Satisfaction (Z), and Net Benefit (Y), have AVE values above the minimum threshold of 0.50, specifically 0.685; 0.742; 0.692; 0.839; and 0.574, respectively. These values indicate that more than 50% of the variance in the indicators can be explained by each construct, meaning that the indicators validly represent the constructs. Additionally, the communalilty values of all variables also exceed the threshold of 0.70, with User Satisfaction having the highest value of 0.916 and Net Benefit the lowest at 0.758. This indicates that the indicators used are highly capable of explaining their respective constructs. Thus, these results confirm that all constructs in the model have convergent validity and strong indicator contributions, allowing the model to proceed to the stage of analyzing relationships between latent variables (inner model) and testing hypotheses as a whole.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity testing was conducted to prove whether the indicators in a construct would have the largest factor loading in the construct it formed rather than factor loading in other constructs. Cross loading can be seen in Table 3.

Table 2. Cross Loading

Indicators Quality	System Quality (X1)	Information Quality (X2)	Service Satisfaction (X3)	Users Benefits (Z)	Clean (Y)
X1.1	0,794	0,685	0,649	0,354	0,387
X1.2	0,843	0,659	0,643	0,194	0,435
X1.3	0,859	0,700	0,647	0,226	0,473
X1.4	0,827	0,715	0,611	0,162	0,512
X1.5	0,768	0,652	0,541	0,135	0,415
X1.6	0,869	0,729	0,725	0,373	0,516
X2.1	0,800	0,916	0,728	0,331	0,427
X2.2	0,650	0,799	0,605	0,085	0,272
X2.3	0,701	0,900	0,681	0,226	0,342
X2.4	0,702	0,824	0,651	0,181	0,406
X3.1	0,718	0,754	0,830	0,336	0,448
X3.2	0,698	0,758	0,753	0,248	0,412

Indicators Quality	System Quality (X1)	Information Quality (X2)	Service Satisfaction (X3)	Users Benefits (Z)	Clean (Y)
X3.3	0,705	0,776	0,858	0,392	0,436
X3.4	0,608	0,520	0,881	0,724	0,432
Z1	0,314	0,280	0,525	0,878	0,334
Z2	0,259	0,221	0,478	0,918	0,199
Z3	0,329	0,257	0,607	0,950	0,320
Y.1	0,218	0,183	0,183	0,088	0,412
Y.2	0,531	0,453	0,518	0,312	0,806
Y.3	0,478	0,414	0,363	0,232	0,857
Y.4	0,364	0,297	0,305	0,124	0,793
Y.5	0,391	0,242	0,422	0,298	0,830

Based on Table 3 above, the cross-loading values also indicate good discriminant validity because the correlation values of the indicators with their constructs are higher than the correlation values of the indicators with other constructs. For example, the loading factor for System Quality (X1), where Information Quality (X2), Service Quality (X3), User Satisfaction (Z), and Net Benefits (Y) have smaller values than the indicators X1.1, X1.2, X1.3, X1.4, X1.5, and X1.6 in the System Quality (X1) variable. The table also shows that these indicators have the same magnitude of relationship as the loading factors with other constructs. A similar pattern is observed for the indicators in Information Quality (X2), Service Quality (X3), User Satisfaction (Z), and Net Benefits (Y). Thus, the latent constructs predict the indicators, influence each other, and are interdependent among the variables.

Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha

In addition to construct validity testing, construct reliability testing was also conducted, measured using composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha from the indicator blocks that measure the construct. The following are the results of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha testing from SmartPLS.

Table 3. Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
System Quality (X1)	0,912	0,929
Information Quality (X2)	0,894	0,920
Service Satisfaction (X3)	0,867	0,900
Users Benefits (Z)	0,904	0,940
Clean (Y)	0,809	0,865

A construct is considered reliable if it has a composite reliability value above 0.70 and a Cronbach's alpha above 0.60. From the SmartPLS output above, all constructs have a composite reliability value above 0.70 and a Cronbach's alpha above 0.60. Therefore, it can be concluded that the constructs have good reliability.

Hypothesis Testing

The structural model in PLS is evaluated using R^2 for dependent variables and path coefficients for independent variables, with significance assessed based on the t-statistic for each path. The structural model of this study is presented in the following figure:

Figure 2. Structural Model Output View

Table 5. Path Coefficient (Mean, STDEV, and t-Value)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	t-Statistic (O/STDEV)	P-Value
System Quality (X1) -> User Satisfaction (Z)	-0.113	-0.125	0.125	0.908	0.364
Information Quality (X2) -> User Satisfaction (Z)	0.404	-0.363	0.152	2.661	0.008
Quality of Service (X3) -> User Satisfaction (Z)	0.996	0.983	0.105	9.517	0.000
User Satisfaction (Z) -> Net Benefit (Y)	0.316	0.341	0.076	4.165	0.000

The hypothesis test results indicate that system quality has no significant effect on user satisfaction (H1 is rejected). In contrast, information quality and service quality have a positive and significant impact on user satisfaction (H2 and H3 are accepted). Additionally, user satisfaction is found to positively and significantly affect net benefits (H4 is accepted).

The Influence of System Quality on User Satisfaction

This study found that system quality does not significantly affect user satisfaction, with a p-value of 0.364 and a t-statistic of 0.908, which are below the threshold for

significance. Although previous studies (e.g., Al-Athmay et al., 2016; Aldholay et al., 2018; Alzahrani et al., 2019) found a positive relationship between system quality and user satisfaction, this research does not support that conclusion.

System quality refers to the combination of hardware and software that meets user needs, while user satisfaction is the users' response to their experience. Despite system quality being crucial in prior studies, other factors like customer service quality, accessibility, and system functionality may influence satisfaction more. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) suggests that system quality affects satisfaction through Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), but this study indicates that technical quality alone may not improve user satisfaction. A more holistic experience, including user interaction and operational support, may be required.

In conclusion, the study challenges the view that system quality directly impacts user satisfaction, suggesting that other factors play a more significant role. Further research is needed to explore these influences in information systems.

The Influence of Information Quality on User Satisfaction

This study found that information quality significantly impacts user satisfaction, with a p-value of 0.008 and a t-statistic of 2.661, supporting the hypothesis. This aligns with previous research (Al Athmay et al., 2016; Aldholay et al., 2018; Alzahrani et al., 2019), which highlights the positive effect of information quality on user satisfaction.

Information quality, including accuracy, completeness, timeliness, and format, plays a key role in user satisfaction. When users receive relevant, understandable, and useful information, satisfaction increases. According to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), information quality affects satisfaction through Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). High-quality information enhances PU by improving performance and influences PEOU by making the system easier to use.

In conclusion, the study confirms that good information quality is vital for user satisfaction. For systems like SAKTI and PPNPN, improving information quality is essential to enhance user experience.

The Influence of Service Quality on User Satisfaction

The study shows that service quality significantly impacts user satisfaction, with a p-value of 0.000 and a t-statistic of 9.517, supporting the hypothesis. This is consistent with previous studies (Mu'minah and Metalica, 2022; Aboelmaged, 2018; Almaiah and Alismaiel, 2019) that found a positive relationship between service quality and user satisfaction.

Service quality, defined as the gap between user expectations and perceptions of service, includes IT support, responsiveness, competence, and empathy. Users are more satisfied when services meet or exceed expectations. According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), service quality affects satisfaction through attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. A positive attitude and community influence enhance satisfaction, while easy access and timely solutions improve user experience.

In conclusion, service quality significantly influences user satisfaction in systems like SAKTI and PPNPN. To boost satisfaction, administrators should focus on improving responsiveness, competence, and accessibility.

The Influence of User Satisfaction on Net Benefit

This study finds that user satisfaction significantly impacts the net benefits derived from using an information system, with a p-value of 0.000 and a t-statistic of 5.145. These results align with previous research (Pambudi et al., 2022; Al-Zahrani, 2020; Bradford et al., 2020), showing that higher user satisfaction leads to greater benefits, such as increased efficiency and better outcomes.

User satisfaction, as defined by Seddon and Kiew (1996), results from users' positive experiences with the system's performance and effectiveness. Satisfied users experience improved productivity and efficiency, which enhances both individual and organizational performance. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) suggests that satisfaction strengthens positive attitudes toward technology use and encourages continued usage, boosting perceived net benefits.

In conclusion, the study highlights that higher user satisfaction with systems like SAKTI and PPNPN leads to greater perceived benefits. Improving user experience is essential for enhancing organizational performance and sustaining the system's effectiveness.

Conclusion

The study on the implementation of the SAKTI and PPNPN applications in Mataram City's work units reveals that system quality does not significantly impact user satisfaction, likely due to external factors like customer service and ease of access. However, information quality significantly enhances user satisfaction, aligning with previous research that highlights the importance of accurate, complete, and timely information. Service quality also plays a crucial role, with a positive impact on satisfaction through support, responsiveness, and competence. Furthermore, user satisfaction strongly influences the net benefits derived from the system, driving productivity, efficiency, and continued use. These findings emphasize the need for improved information and service quality to optimize user experience and system performance.

Based on the research findings, work units in Mataram City should prioritize improving the system's technical quality, focusing on ease of use and alignment with user needs. They should ensure the system provides accurate, complete, timely, and understandable information, as this significantly impacts user satisfaction. Enhancing service quality through responsiveness, competence, and empathy is crucial to meeting user expectations. Additionally, to increase net benefits, work units should improve user experience through better accessibility, operational support, and problem resolution. Organizing training programs and providing adequate technical support will also help users optimize system usage, boosting satisfaction and overall system performance.

Research Implications

The results of this study have significant implications for the development and strengthening of government information systems, particularly in the context of financial and personnel administration management within work units. The implementation of the SAKTI and PPNPN applications has been proven to have an impact on service quality and work efficiency, as reflected in the System Quality, Information Quality, Service Quality, and User Satisfaction indicators, which show a positive contribution to Net Benefit.

Practically, these results serve as a basis for policymakers at the ministry and work unit levels to make continuous improvements to application features, enhance operator training, and provide more responsive technical support. The high level of user satisfaction also indicates that the application is sufficiently adaptive to the needs of work units, but further strengthening of the Net Benefit aspect is still required to maximize the long-term benefits of the application's implementation.

From an academic perspective, this research enriches the literature in the field of public sector information systems, particularly in the application of evaluation models such as the DeLone and McLean Information System Success Model in the Indonesian government work environment. This research can also serve as a reference for further studies exploring the integration of other digital systems in the context of bureaucratic reform and improving the quality of public services based on information technology.

Research Contributions

Contributions to the Government

This research provides important contributions to the government, particularly in formulating more targeted policies for the implementation of financial information technology. The findings that there is still a decline in the effectiveness of the SAKTI application, infrastructure constraints, and increased delays in PPNPN payments indicate that the challenges of implementing web-based systems have not yet been fully addressed. Therefore, the results of this research can be used as a basis for developing more intensive and sustainable training policies for application users, strengthening infrastructure support across all regions, and enhancing system capacity. The government is also encouraged to regularly evaluate the performance of the application and adjust features that are less relevant to operational needs on the ground. As a result, the digitalization of financial systems will become more effective, efficient, and equitable.

Contribution to Application Users

For users of the SAKTI application, particularly employees directly involved in the financial administration and payroll processes for PPNPN, this study provides practical insights into the importance of enhancing individual capacity in operating web-based systems. The research indicates that basic training alone is insufficient to address the complexity of the application's features, necessitating advanced understanding to ensure more accurate and efficient work processes. In addition, users also need to be more active

in providing feedback on the obstacles they face so that it can be used as evaluation material for system developers. In this context, users are not only technical implementers but also important actors in supporting the successful implementation of the system. This study encourages the creation of a work culture that is adaptive to technology and collaborative in finding solutions to emerging financial administration problems.

Contribution to Future Research

This study provides a foundation for further research on digital transformation in state financial management, particularly through the use of web-based SAKTI applications. By evaluating the shift from desktop to web-based systems and examining its impact on users and administrative processes, this study opens up new opportunities for broader exploration, both conceptually and methodologically. Future researchers can build on this study using quantitative approaches to statistically measure the influence between variables, or in-depth qualitative approaches to explore user perceptions at various levels of bureaucracy. Additionally, comparative studies between regions or institutions could serve as an alternative to assess the success of system implementation within different geographical and institutional contexts. Thus, this research not only contributes practically but also enriches the academic literature in the field of public sector information systems.

Research Limitations

1. This study was only conducted in Mataram City, so the findings may not be fully generalizable to other regions or contexts. Further research could include other regions to obtain a broader picture.
2. This study focuses solely on system quality, information quality, service quality, and user satisfaction as primary variables. Future research may consider additional variables that may influence the effectiveness and efficiency of using the SAKTI and PPNPN applications, such as organizational factors, policies, or work culture.
3. This study uses a quantitative method with data collection through surveys. This method can be complemented with qualitative approaches, such as interviews or focus group discussions (FGD), to delve deeper into users' experiences and perceptions of the system.
4. This study does not consider external factors that may influence user satisfaction, such as government policies or recent technological developments. Future research may include an analysis of external factors that may influence the implementation and use of the system.
5. This study was conducted over a specific period of time, which may not reflect the dynamics of system use in the long term. Further research could involve longitudinal studies to observe changes in user satisfaction and benefits over time.
6. This study relies on subjective data from users regarding their satisfaction and the benefits they have gained. Future research could use objective data, such as performance results or system usage efficiency, to provide a more complete picture.

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